

Voices from the Horizon

Third Countries'
Experiences
Guiding the Design
of FP10

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Abstract

The globalization of Horizon Europe (FP9), the European Union's (EU) key funding programme for research and innovation (R&I), has been an ambitious endeavour, expanding collaboration between excellent researchers and innovators across the globe. With longstanding partners such as Moldova, Türkiye, the United Kingdom (UK), Switzerland, and countries from the European Economic Area (EEA) continuing their commitment to Framework Programmes (FP), the EU has opened doors for new partnerships to form. Newly associated partners now include New Zealand, Canada, and South Korea, bringing together a diverse wealth of expertise. As the largest international programme for research and innovation, associating to Horizon Europe presents a compelling opportunity for non-EU countries, although it requires a significant commitment, including financial contributions, alignment with EU research priorities, and participation in collaborative projects for up to seven years. The fact that not all eligible countries decide to associate, with Australia declining to join the programme, underscores the complexity and multifaceted nature of the internationalization process, highlighting that the global expansion of Horizon Europe warrants thorough exploration.

As the EU prepares for the design negotiations of Framework Programme 10 (FP10),

it is therefore crucial to understand what works well in terms of the internationalization of Horizon Europe and what could be improved going forward. This study aims to serve as a gateway to fostering an open discussion on the operationalization of openness in international research and innovation cooperation between the EU and third countries to ensure mutual benefits.

While the voices of Member States are reflected in the design of Framework Programmes, the collective voices of third countries may not be as prominent in Brussels, and this report aims to provide an invitation to address that. Based on the analysis of qualitative and quantitative data from semi-structured interviews with participants from third countries that have engaged in negotiations on association to Horizon Europe, this report offers a comprehensive overview of the points of satisfaction and concerns of these third countries. Key recommendations include ensuring the inclusion of third countries' voices at the design stage, establishing FP10 early enough for timely association, and providing more clarity on association terms. Additionally, offering financial safeguards, considering practical challenges such as time zones and language, and including phased participation of National Contact Points (NCPs) in meetings are emphasized. Streamlining the application process, strengthening fora for discussion, and considering country categorisation to reflect historical partnerships are also recommended. Additional recommendations specific to third countries are included, highlighting the importance of all parties working together.

These insights and recommendations are intended to assist the European Commission and third countries in fostering dialogue and designing a more inclusive and mutually beneficial FP10, enhancing global collaboration in research and innovation.

Introduction

The European Union's key funding programme for research and innovation, Horizon Europe launched in 2021, allows participation from countries outside the EU, which can join as associated or non-associated countries. While all third countries (with a few exceptions) can participate, associating to the programme allows their R&I communities to be beneficiaries of projects and be funded directly by the Horizon Europe budget. The Horizon Europe strategic plan 2021-2024 (European Commission, 2021a) introduced the extension of association possibilities as one of the key novelties of the programme, leading to change in openness and furthering international collaboration. The major difference between Horizon 2020 (FP8), the predecessor of Horizon Europe, and Horizon Europe in this aspect was a departure from the criterion based on association to the previous Framework Programme (category C in FP8) and the addition of a new criterion allowing 'like-minded' third countries that *'fulfil a set of scientific, economic and political criteria'* (category D in Article 16.1 of the Horizon Europe Regulation 2021/695 (European Union, 2021)) to negotiate association. Going beyond existing partnerships for European or neighbouring countries, this has broadened the pool of potential associated countries around the globe including Canada and Australia, which were interviewed as part of this study (the latter has not associated to Horizon Europe).

The process of associating and subsequently participating in Horizon Europe, the European Union's (EU) flagship research and innovation programme, is a critical yet complex issue for third countries. This report **aims** to explore their experiences and the challenges and opportunities of the association process, with a particular focus on Framework Programme 9 (FP9). It emphasizes the need for third countries' voices to be included in the design of the forthcoming Framework Programme 10 (FP10).

The **originality** of this research lies in its comprehensive analysis of the barriers faced by third countries and its advocacy for a more

inclusive approach. We believe this is the first research study to neutrally represent the diverse voices of third countries on this matter. The recommendations are based on both qualitative and quantitative evidence from interviews, thereby adding an important human dimension to the analysis. This approach highlights the need to consider not only the economic costs and benefits but also the human experiences and perspectives in the decision-making process. This report explores the global aspirations of the programme and how its **openness can be operationalised** more effectively from the perspective of third countries with mutual benefit in mind.

The **timeliness** of this research cannot be overstated. As the EU prepares for the FP10 design negotiations, it is crucial to ensure that third countries' voices are represented. The EU's Global Approach to Research and Innovation strategy (European Commission, 2021b) emphasizes openness and international collaboration, yet there are still significant hurdles that need to be overcome.

By bringing attention to these critical aspects, this report seeks to open a discussion on how to better integrate third countries into Horizon Europe and future Framework Programmes, ultimately **fostering a more collaborative and inclusive** global research and innovation community.

Semi-structured interviews were used in this study to gain insights into third countries' experiences with associating to Horizon Europe. Participants were asked 12 open questions and 12 numerical ones and prompted to expand on subjects or matters that they deemed significant. Interviews took approximately 1 hour and were conducted online using Microsoft Teams. We collected 9 hours and 53 minutes of recordings and 252 pages of qualitative and quantitative data that were analysed to form a basis for findings and recommendations presented in this report. Standard ethical procedures were followed.

Participants were identified through their role and involvement with FP9 and European Union matters, coming from a range of national public organisations from third countries. The process of contacting participants was subject to the researchers' contacts and networks, and it was regrettably not feasible to encompass the totality of third countries engaging with FP9. Despite this limitation, the report provides diverse perspectives and emerging themes, offering significant insights and contributing to the broader understanding of the topic. Participants had the choice to remain completely anonymous or have their country (by which we mean the country of the organisation and not necessarily the nationality of the participants) and name mentioned, or only their country mentioned.

The participants who agreed to be identified are:

- **Çağrı Yıldırım**, Head of EU Framework Programmes Department at TÜBİTAK, in Türkiye; TR
- **Doinita Ulinici**, Head of the Moldovan Office of Science and Technology within National Agency for Research and Development -

- and **Vitalie Moraru**, Head of the National Office Horizon Europe Moldova within National Agency for Research and Development; President of Moldovan Technology Transfer Network (counted as one respondent); MD

- **Sanaa Zebakh**, Director of cooperation and partnership at the Ministry of Higher Education, Scientific Research and Innovation of Morocco; MA
- **Simon Marti**, Head of Office of SwissCore at the time of the interview; CH
- **Sóley Gréta Sveinsdóttir Morthens**, Councillor at Ministry for Foreign Affairs and Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of Iceland; IS.

Interviews were conducted with a total of 12 respondents from 9 countries (including two participants from Türkiye, the United Kingdom, and Switzerland), from 4 categories as specified by Article 16 of the Horizon Europe Regulation 2021/695 (European Union, 2021) (Table 1), allowing to get insights into a range of different contexts and the unique motivations driving these countries' engagement with Horizon Europe.

Table 1. Interview participants by Horizon Europe country category

Article 16 Category	Definition (EFTA – European Free Trade Association, EEA – European Economic Area)	Countries (At the time of the interview: A – associated, A* – associated to Pillar II, A** – associated except EIC fund, NA – not associated, TA – transitional agreement)
A	Members of EFTA, which are members of the EEA	Norway (A), Iceland (A)
B	Acceding countries, candidates and potential candidates	Türkiye (A), Moldova (A)
C	European Neighbourhood Policy countries	Moldova (A), Morocco (TA)
D	Third countries and territories that fulfil a set of scientific, economic and political criteria	UK (A**), Switzerland (TA), Canada (A*), Australia (NA)

The views and opinions expressed in this document are solely those of the participants and are not representative of their country's official position. Interview participants will be referred to in the text as 'participants', 'respondents', or 'interviewees'.

This report is organized into four sections. It starts with the motivations behind third countries' engagement with the programme. This section is followed by the challenges they faced during the distinct stages of association, starting with the decision to associate, followed by the association process, and then participation. The report concludes with the future directions for the next iteration of the framework. Recommendations are included throughout the report and summarized in the final section for convenience.

I. Why Third Countries Chose to Engage with Horizon Europe ‘You do better science when you are together.’ (UK)

The EU's Global Approach to Research and Innovation (European Commission, 2021b) emphasizes openness and promoting a level playing field, aiming to foster collaboration with a diverse range of third countries. From EEA/EFTA countries participating in Framework Programmes as early as 1994, neighbouring or candidate countries with diverse economies and long-term partnerships, to new and geographically distant countries, associating

to Horizon Europe is a decision supported by the acknowledgement of a **series of perceived benefits**.

In this section, we explore the various incentives to associate to the 9th edition of Framework Programmes that participants highlighted during the interviews, ranked according to their responses (See Figure 1).

Figure 1: Top incentives to association to Horizon Europe

where UK - United Kingdom, NO - Norway, CH - Switzerland, IS - Iceland, MD - Moldova, AU - Australia, TR - Türkiye, MA - Morocco

The categories represent the most frequently cited incentives. The number indicates how many participants ranked each incentive within their top 3.

1.1. Scale

All interviewees highlighted the attractiveness of participating in the **largest collaborative R&I programme worldwide** and the scientific and innovation partnerships that it fosters internationally between industrial, academic, and civil communities. Horizon Europe is perceived as a bridge to developing and maintaining active partnerships using one, already well-established and bureaucratically supported, vehicle. For countries from outside of Europe, Horizon Europe allows them to deepen partnerships with European counterparts, whereas for European countries like Norway *'it's also an important arena for cooperation with countries outside of Europe'* (NO).

Scale is also related to the **scope of opportunities** offered by Horizon Europe, especially related to the multi-million large consortia project opportunities in Pillar II 'Global challenges'. The six thematic clusters supporting progress within key priorities such as for example, Health (Cluster 1) and Climate, Energy and Mobility (Cluster 5) through top-down calls allow third countries *'to do research on global challenges which go beyond the capacity of one single country'* (CH). For smaller countries in particular, *'that's the only real way to approach global challenges and participate in [the] global research environment'* (IS) and it is a *'lifeline for the universities and the research and innovation environment in Iceland'* (IS).

1.2. Excellence and competition

Increased **competition** fostering **excellence** under the guise of Horizon Europe's high evaluation standards amongst a pool of reputed participating organisations is the **second highest incentive** mentioned by interviewees. One anonymous Swiss respondent stated that *'it offers our researchers [the opportunity] to compete in an international context'*, highlighting the positive impact on individual careers once they *'prove themselves on an international parquet and they get the possibility to work with the best all around Europe and beyond'*.

As highlighted by a British participant, Horizon Europe extends benefits to institutions as well: *'for our big universities doing key technologies, it's important to be at the table.'*

These positive impacts at the micro level (i.e. the level of an individual and the R&I community), in turn, yield broader benefits for associated third countries. In the case of the EU candidate country Moldova, interviewees reported that Horizon Europe allows them to *'leverage [...] the expertise and best practices from the leading European researchers and institutions, and this fact can accelerate the development of the country's own research [and] innovation capabilities'* (MD).

Similarly, a Norwegian respondent noted that *'the participation in the framework programmes had substantially increased the quality of the research and innovation. It made positive contributions to competitiveness.'*

1.3. International relations

As a landmark on the international scene, Horizon Europe offers a real opportunity for third countries to contribute to global discussions in research and innovation. Following the departure of the UK from the EU in 2020, one UK respondent noted that *'Being part of Horizon allows the UK to be part of broader policy discussions in the European Research Area and to kind of - through that - shape international standards and norms and forge links with partners.'*

When asked about the potential impacts of associating to FP9 on third countries' ability to engage with other national and international R&I programmes, no significant challenges were reported, with an average score of 8 and 7.2 out of 10 respectively (see Figure 2). In fact, it was noted by a British interviewee that **an associated status may render a third country more attractive to non-associated countries** who see bilateral collaboration as a *'gateway to further engagement and building links within the European Union.'*

Figure 3: Alignment of FP9's themes and structures with national priorities

To what extent do FP9's themes (blue) / structure (yellow) align with your national priorities? (1 - Not at all; 10 Very good alignment)

Themes - Average: 8; Lowest: 7; Highest: 9
 Structure - Average: 7.3; Lowest: 5; Highest: 9

1.5. Visibility and prestige

Participating in Horizon Europe, especially within mobility instruments in Pillar I such as Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA), which promote opportunities including Doctoral Networks, Postdoctoral Fellowships, or Staff Exchanges, can help third countries become **more attractive** to the global community of researchers and innovators. This benefit is shared across participants from the UK highlighting that Horizon Europe offers *'the ability to attract talented researchers from abroad to come to the UK and to perform their research and potentially forge their careers there as well'*, and Iceland stating that Horizon Europe helps *'draw researchers to Iceland, to make it feasible for people that have studied abroad, also for Icelanders, because many or most in Iceland take their PhD abroad, to come back and have a realistic career.'* Attracting researchers was also reported to **yield benefits for younger generations**, as one interviewee from Iceland remarked that it provided Icelandic students with *'a quality education with talented teachers and researchers and creative work environment.'*

Box 1: Horizon Europe Instruments

When third countries refer to the programming of Horizon Europe, it encompasses various instruments within the three-pillar structure. These pillars include:

Pillar I
'Excellent Science' bolsters bottom-up basic research and researchers' career development. It includes: European Research Council (ERC), Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA), and Research Infrastructures.

Pillar II
'Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness' addresses six thematic clusters through large collaborative top-down grants. It includes the Joint Research Centre (JCR).

Pillar III
'Innovative Europe' enables the development of innovative products and services and supports Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SME). It includes: European Innovation Council (EIC), European Innovation Ecosystems, and European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT).

as well as the five EU Missions and Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area initiative (WIDERA).

Additionally, one participant stated that Türkiye pursues association partly for **market integration** as: *'It's about the companies. They have products and then with the involvement in the collaboration projects, they can introduce their products in different countries'* (TR).

Moreover, **visibility** goes beyond attracting foreign talent and builds up **prestige** within national R&I communities, raising a country's ranking, as expressed by one Moroccan respondent. For Turkish and Australian researchers alike, prestige was among the top drivers to consider association: *'The main motivation actually is that the programme is very, very prestigious for the Turkish researchers and the ecosystems.'* (TR)

1.6. Evaluating association incentives

In addition to the incentives mentioned in previous sub-sections, a few participants highlighted **financial incentives**, namely that participating in Horizon Europe yielded greater economic returns through increased funding. However, the primary incentives to associate, as identified through these interviews, are predominantly **non-monetary benefits**. These are harder to quantify, making the decision to associate a complex one, where financial, social, societal and broader economic and – as we shall see later – political considerations are interwoven.

Recommendation 1 (3rd) When considering association, take into account both monetary and non-monetary benefits to the economy and the society, including the research and innovation (R&I) community.

1.7. Common ground for strengthened collaboration

The wide range of incentives and benefits from association mentioned by the participants coincide with the reasons why the European Commission finds it critical to engage with international partners. As stated in a 2024 independent evaluation report on Horizon Europe commissioned by the European Commission, **'[International collaboration is] among the key priorities of the Union'** (European Commission, 2024a). Indeed, the participation of international partners as associated countries in Horizon Europe is recognised as a driver of **world-class research**. The European Commission evaluation report (European Commission, 2024a) highlights specifically the following motivations:

- **Knowledge and Expertise Exchange** (discussed in [Excellence and Competition](#) section 1.2.)
- **Leveraging Resources** (discussed in [Scale](#) section)
- **Global Problem Solving** (discussed in [Scale](#) section 1.1.)
- **Enhanced Competitiveness** (discussed in [Excellence and competition](#) section 1.2.)
- **Attracting Talent** (discussed in [Visibility and prestige](#) section 1.5.)
- **Market Access** (discussed in [Visibility and prestige](#) section 1.5.)

This alignment provides a strong building block towards exploring **mutually beneficial solutions** to association and participation **challenges** mentioned by third countries, which we discuss in the next section.

II. Challenges Faced by Third Countries in Framework Programme 9

Although for some interviewees association seems like *'it's a no brainer'* (IS) and *'it's just the most obvious thing to do'* (CH), there are numerous perceived challenges that can complicate this decision and its implementation. Following a chronological

approach from **considering association** to **associating to Horizon Europe** and finally **participating as an associated third country**, this section highlights the key challenges that affect third countries' experiences with FP9 (See Figure 4).

Figure 4: Top challenges to association to Horizon Europe

where UK - United Kingdom, NO - Norway, CH - Switzerland, IS - Iceland, MD - Moldova, AU - Australia, TR - Türkiye, MA - Morocco

The categories represent the most frequently cited challenges. The number indicates how many participants ranked each challenge within their top 3.

2.1. Challenges during the consideration stage *'It was kind of assumed that third countries would want to associate.'* (AU)

The consideration stage, where a third country weighs the potential benefits of association against potential costs and risks, depends on that country's internal decision-making procedures, which include economic, political, and strategic considerations. However, this pivotal step also relies on the **perceived quality of information** made available to third countries and can be influenced by feelings of **uncertainty**.

For newly eligible third countries (subject to economic and like-mindedness criteria specified under Article 16.1 of the Horizon Europe Regulation 2021/695 (European Union, 2021)), this deliberation period is even more critical, as they navigate the terms of committing to the 7-year Framework Programme for the first time. In this context, the initial contact between the EU and the third country is significant. Regarding the approach of the EU to inviting new countries, one Australian participant expressed a sense of **confusion**: *'It was kind of assumed that third countries would want to associate. But there was never a formal invitation to associate by the European Commission, and so it was a really weird dance',* and added that *'There was a long period in which we were being asked to express an opinion about association in which we had no idea what we'd be signing up for.'* An unclear invitation process could discourage a third country from pursuing association, as it requires them to express interest, thereby exposing them politically without any guarantee of what they will be able to access or the terms that will apply.

2.1.1. Transparency of association terms

As mentioned in the previous paragraph, perceived **transparency** is important as third countries need to feel confident in making an informed decision on associating to a Framework Programme. Respondents rated

the transparency of association terms an average of 7.5 out of 10 (See Figure 5), all giving high scores (7 or above), except for Turkish respondents who gave an average score of 3.5 out of 10, one of whom said that technical aspects within the terms of their association were subsequently changed, such as the costs of overheads for referees.

With participants mostly satisfied with the clarity of guidelines and procedures, a few mentioned room for further clarification, while others recognised that minor details can pose challenges and referenced issues in the implementation of restrictions (see Section 2.3.1).

Recommendation 2 (EC) Provide more clarity and transparency for third countries about association terms, especially financial, governance and restrictions.

Figure 5: Transparency of association terms

To what extent are FP9's terms of association transparent? (1 - Not transparent; 10 - Very transparent)

Average: 7.5; Lowest: 3; Highest: 9

2.1.2. Financial terms

The financial terms play an important role for third countries when considering association. Decision-makers are bearing in mind the **'value for money'** that association brings to their country, weighing the previously mentioned benefits (See Section I) against the costs.

In practice, associating to Horizon Europe functions on the basis of an operational contribution and a participation fee that are to be paid bi-annually as stated on the association agreement. The ever-rising budget for Framework Programmes, currently at 95.5 billion euros for Horizon Europe, may incur higher participation costs for associated third countries, thereby justifying the need for a thorough 'value for money' analysis. Financial terms were ranked within the top 3 challenges by 7 out of 12 participants (See Figure 4) - especially on the **uncertainty** around the amount of third countries' contribution: *'the funding model, the inability to determine how much our contribution would be, is the biggest challenge... It does not fit well with our fiscal system. It's a very difficult thing for the Australian government to write a blank cheque to the research and innovation sector based on their success. I think it's just that feeling of risk, as it builds over time, there will be no way of turning off that tap of funding...'* (AU). Concerns about **the lack of a spending cap** for associated third countries were shared by Canadian and Turkish participants.

Beyond the amount itself and the lack of spending cap, the **calculation methods** for the participation fee were also criticized by an anonymous participant from Türkiye: *'It's very obscure. It's like only three people on this planet know how it is calculated. And of course, we have mutual trust among the Commission, but it would be better if we knew how it was calculated.'*

The lack of financial safeguards for associated third countries could lead to potentially unlimited financial exposure, a clear obstacle at the consideration stage. There is a need for transparency in these methods, as one

anonymous interviewee from Türkiye expressed concerns over current practices: *'Nobody should have to meet over coffee and compare their association agreements. It's not very nice.'*

Figure 6: Challenge associated with financial terms

To what extent were FP9's financial terms a challenge during association? (1 - Not a challenge; 10 - Huge challenge)

Average: 5.8; Lowest: 2; Highest: 10

Responses are illustrated using inverted scale. Original question asked on a scale: 1 - Huge challenge, 10 - Not a challenge.

When asked to rate the extent to which financial terms were a challenge during the association process, responses varied across interviewed participants, with an average of 5.8 out of 10 (where 10 indicates huge challenge, and 1 indicates not a challenge) (See Figure 6). While respondents from Australia and the UK are on one side of the spectrum rating it as 10 and 9 respectively (huge challenge) - on the other side of the spectrum are respondents from Switzerland (2), Iceland (3), and Moldova (4). One Australian respondent noted *'That barrier of not being able to set the amount of money felt like an insurmountable barrier for us'*, and shared concern over a treaty *'where we can't control the spend without risking reputational damage'* (meaning risk for the Australian government vis-à-vis the research sector if participation costs became too high to sustain association).

However, while finding financial terms extremely challenging during association, the UK has uniquely managed to negotiate a 'clawback' mechanism ensuring that *'the UK will be compensated should UK scientists receive significantly less money than the UK puts into the programme.'* (UK Government, 2023a)

On the contrary, participants from Norway, Moldova, and Iceland, while acknowledging the internal challenge associated with unlocking the funds necessary to associate, did not consider the terms problematic. An interviewee from Iceland stated that *'it's a lot of money, so we have to prioritise that money into this rather than something else.'* As mentioned in Section 1.6, participants from Iceland and Moldova shared that the ability to access increased funding through associating to Horizon Europe was, in fact, **a top incentive** to associate.

To conclude, the challenging nature of financial terms is shared among interviewees but may differ depending on whether it springs from an **internal challenge** (unlocking the public fund, aligning fiscal systems, risk of reputational damage), an **external challenge** (uncertainty, lack of clarity and guarantees such as a spending cap), or both. It is important to note here that, as part of the EEA agreements, financial terms are already set for Norway and Iceland and were not an item of negotiation for Horizon Europe.

Recommendation 3 (EC) Offer financial safeguards opportunities to all third countries, to limit the risk of financial exposure related to participation.

2.1.3. Consideration of third countries' voices at the design stage

As part of the decision to associate, assessing the alignment of third countries' interests with the global aims of the framework programme is central. Interviewees were asked to rate how much their countries' interests were represented in the design of FP9. With an

average of 6.7 out of 10, responses varied greatly from 2 to 9, with the distribution of votes split between more positive ones from the UK, Norway, Switzerland, Canada, Moldova and Iceland, and less positive ones from Australia, Morocco, and Türkiye (See Figure 7). Revealing vastly different experiences regarding the perceived consideration of third countries' interests, these results indicate that further mechanisms for including the voices of third countries **at the design stage** may be considered for FP10 to ensure that the programme is attractive to them. Relevant recommendation to address this challenge will be provided in Section 2.3.6. (See **Recommendation 12**).

Figure 7: Representation of national interest in the design of FP9

To what extent are your country's interests represented in the design of FP9? (1 - Not at all; 10 - Very well represented)

Average: 6.7; Lowest: 2; Highest: 9

2.2. Challenges during the association stage

'Association was always the goal of our government.' (CH, anonymous)

Associating to Horizon Europe is a complex negotiation and legal process between the third country and the EU, which includes agreeing on terms of association and aligning R&I systems to ensure smooth implementation of collaborative opportunities. The legal instruments to associate to Horizon Europe are set out in the Horizon Europe Regulation 2021/695 (European Union, 2021). Apart from EEA countries, whose association is set by the cooperation framework agreed in the EEA agreement, third countries must negotiate and sign an **international agreement** with the EU, some of which are available on the Official Journal of the European Union database (European Union, n.d.).

Based on the interviews, the following key elements were identified as playing an important role **during the process of association**.

2.2.1. Achieving inclusive global internationalization in Horizon Europe

Interviewed participants from category D countries (see Table 1) were supportive of the openness of the programme to like-minded countries. Interviewees from Norway and Türkiye also expressed explicit approval, with one anonymous Turkish participant advocating for global inclusivity: *'I think it should still be open to the whole world and I think that's very valuable. (...) Even if it stays on paper, it still gives the idea that we are one humanity and the humanity advances on research together.'* The latter added: *'But I don't think it [openness] will [continue]. I think the current politics will not allow it if it continues like this. I think at some point there will be choices.'*

It is worth noting that newer countries in category D, such as Canada, New Zealand or Australia, are currently only invited to join Pillar II, although Canadian and Australian respondents expressed an interest towards other instruments within the fund, such as Pillar I.

Recommendation 4 (EC) Consider allowing association to more than Pillar II to all countries from D category.

Moreover, Swiss participants have reservations about theirs and the United Kingdom's place in category D among new countries, due to their long history of collaboration with the EU.

Recommendation 5 (EC) Provide further consideration for country categorisation in the next Framework Programme (e.g. to better reflect historical partnerships).

2.2.2. The Horizon Europe Regulation, a tight timeline for a complex legal process

The Horizon Europe Regulation 2021/695 (European Union, 2021) establishing the programme was published on the 28th of April 2021. This meant that negotiations for third countries could only officially start from that date. A participant from Türkiye noted: *'We lost around 8 months. We had been ready to negotiate before Horizon Europe, but the European Commission was not ready.'* The timeframe between the publication of the Horizon Europe Regulation and the association of third countries varies significantly (See Figure 8).

Figure 8: Timeline of association to Horizon Europe for selected third countries

Amongst other interviewees, a participant from the UK reported that avoiding or minimising delays would be a positive improvement: ***'We want to be able to participate from the very beginning of the programme, for there not to be any delay for that association coming into force, unlike what we've seen with Horizon Europe.'***

Furthermore, the scope and scale of Horizon Europe require that participating countries align their policies with the programme, a process that can be complex and cause further delays. Moldovan participants highlighted it as a main challenge: ***'One of the challenges is administrative barriers aligning the national research and innovation policies and regulations and funding mechanism in the European Framework Programme requirements.'*** While some of the interviewed third countries had participated in Framework Programmes for nearly three decades, the issue of policy alignment and establishing the legal basis for participation are particularly relevant for new category D countries.

A Canadian participant highlighted the **complexity** of transitioning from a third country to an associated country, noting the significant challenges in adapting the agreement to national contexts due to the fact that negotiating with the EU effectively means negotiating with over 27 countries simultaneously.

Recommendation 6 (EC) Ensure that FP10 is established early enough for third countries to associate in a timely manner, preferably to initiate participation at the start of the programme.

Negotiating the association agreement can be **complex and lengthy**, with numerous potential setbacks on the **national** (policy alignment, resources allocation, fiscal systems, legal frameworks adaptation, etc.) and **bilateral** levels (politics surrounding the association, trust, disagreements on specific aspects of the association or programme, etc.), especially under a **'package approach'** (See Box 2).

Box 2: The diplomatic dimension of Horizon Europe – two sides of the same coin

Horizon Europe is a form of **coopetition** and is used as a tool of **science diplomacy** (European Commission, 2025), requiring countries to navigate a balance between **cooperation** – aiming to pool resources to drive innovation to address global challenges, while creating mutual benefits for participating countries – and **competition**, more rooted in national interests and economic growth. These two sides of the same coin create tension between the perceived benefits and challenges that third countries face.

Associating to Horizon Europe means achieving the closest form of scientific collaboration between third countries and the EU. This is not a politically neutral commitment, and association does not happen in a vacuum.

While international relations were mentioned by 7 participants out of 12 as a Top 3 incentive to associate (See Figure 1)...

In its most favourable form, the association is facilitated by or is part of existing agreements. Such is the case for **EEA** countries where the terms of associating to Framework Programmes are already established in the EEA Agreement. For **acceding and candidate countries**, like Moldova and Türkiye, associating to Horizon Europe is part of broader EU integration, under Chapter 25 'Science and Research' of the Acquis Communautaire (European Commission, n.d.a) and serves as a driver for aligning research areas and national programmes to *'integrate [their] research community into [the] European Research Area'* (MD). Notably, a Turkish interviewee stated that the Green Deal had also become a national priority *'thanks to Horizon Europe.'* With long-term goals for EU membership, Moldovan interviewees emphasised that associating to Framework Programmes was self-evident and inscribed within broader efforts *'at this stage, we are negotiating with the EU to be part of the EU, so [...] of course we intend to be associated [to the next Framework Programme].'*

...politics or package approach were mentioned by 6 participants out of 12 as a Top 3 challenge (See Figure 4).

An association agreement can also be subject to a **'package approach'**, where the progress of negotiations is dependent on other agreements unrelated to research and innovation. This approach has been adopted, for example, in the case of Switzerland, where the resolution of other non-related agreements became a requirement for the finalisation of their association to Horizon Europe. One Swiss respondent mentioned, *'But politically there is maybe more resistance on other topics of this package approach, which is why it might take longer negotiating the other agreements on institutional questions and on free movement of persons for instance'* (CH). The EU and Switzerland concluded negotiations in December 2024, almost five years since the start of Horizon Europe.

The UK, which associated to Horizon Europe as a third country after Brexit for the first time, experienced a similar challenge, linked to the Withdrawal Agreement. After multiple delays due to disputes over the Northern Ireland Protocol, financial terms and conditions, which induced the consideration of a new alternative national UK programme, the 'Pioneer Scheme for opportunities beyond Horizon Europe' (UK Government, 2023b), the UK and the EU signed an agreement in Autumn 2023 for the UK's association starting in January 2024.

Two other respondents have also highlighted a heightened political aspect in their engagement with Horizon Europe, including Morocco (still in transitional arrangements as of March 2025) and Türkiye. Turkish participants expressed regret that *'it's politics unfortunately. It shouldn't be politics, but there are politics most of the time'*, with Moroccan counterparts adding that *'it's much more political. It has nothing to do with science.'*

2.2.3. Mitigating the impacts of delays

Delays in negotiations can induce **discontinuity in participation**, which has **short-term consequences** (funding gaps, missed opportunities between partners) and **long-term consequences** (loss of networks, loss of EU-funding specialist skills, etc.).

The UK was particularly affected, as participation rates declined during the association delay between 2021 and 2023, with the number of signed grants falling from 1251 in 2020 to 739 in 2021, 1084 in 2022, and 776 in 2023 (European Commission, Horizon Dashboard, n.d.a).

This dip in participation uptake was partly attributed to the sense of **uncertainty** felt by R&I communities, both in the UK and other participating countries, as to the eligibility of applicants from the UK. One UK respondent mentioned *'Our rate of participation fell quite significantly during that period for obvious reasons. The uncertainty of the lack of leadership possibilities and just the sense of the politics not being great.'* To mitigate the impacts of delays, a **guarantee funding scheme with match-funding** was provided by the national agency UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). Thanks to this programme, British researchers and innovators could apply to Horizon Europe calls as beneficiaries, allowing for full involvement in the bid development (although they could not be coordinators). If successful, their status would be changed to 'associated partner' and they would receive an automatic national match-funding to finance their participation in the project. However, looking ahead, the **lasting impact of the association delay** manifests itself as one UK respondent shared, as a sense of concern *'it's always in the back of your mind that this collaboration or association could be hostage to that kind of political dynamic of the future.'*

Switzerland, the associated third country with the highest participation rate in Horizon 2020 (European Union, Horizon Dashboard, n.d.b), implemented direct funding from the State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) on selected Horizon Europe instruments during transitional arrangements covering their association delay. This alternative funding option had been **pre-**

emptively designed as early as 2020 to ensure the continuity of funding in case the association of Switzerland was to fail or be delayed. Swiss respondents then reasserted that *'Association was always the goal of our government'* and that *'our researchers and innovators work with many actors in Europe; thus, it makes sense to participate and to support a strong participation until we are again associated.'* As such, they did not report a significant drop in participation in the Horizon Europe instruments accessible to Swiss researchers (Pillar II) during the delay (State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation, 2023). While Switzerland mitigated impacts from their delayed association to Horizon Europe with match-funding, one Swiss participant expressed **significant concern regarding the stability of their association** with FP9, rating it a 9 out of 10 (See Figure 9). It is important to note that this interview took place before Switzerland became an associated country in January 2025.

Figure 9: Concern about the stability of association

To what extent is your country concerned about the stability of its association to FP9? (1 - not concerned; 10 - very concerned)

Average: 2.6; Lowest: 1; Highest: 9

Responses are illustrated using inverted scale. Original question asked on a scale: 1 - Very concerned, 10 - Not concerned.

Recommendation 7 (EC) Offer match-funding (e.g. guarantee or direct funding) mechanisms to mitigate impacts of delays on participation.

2.3. Challenges during the participation stage 'You have to have a mindset which is more or less European' (MD)

Months or years of negotiations, if successful, will lead to obtaining an associated third country status. Following this process, a third country can enjoy the opportunity to lead consortia, and the stability of a multi-year commitment. This, in turn, allows associated countries to invest in sustainable capacity building – with replicability of specific knowledge and processes across multiple projects – and maximise the societal and economic impacts of the 7-year programme.

It's worth noting that while the government negotiates and signs the association agreement, participation in the opportunities of the programme ultimately lies with the research and innovation communities of said third country. They will be the ones to become applicants, beneficiaries, and coordinators of Horizon Europe-funded projects. In practice, **ensuring the uptake of Horizon Europe opportunities can be complex.** Participation, ranked as the second top challenge for third countries (see Figure 4), can be impaired due to various reasons such as thematic call restrictions as defined in Article 22.5 of the Horizon Europe Regulation 2021/695 (European Union, 2021), delays, complexity and administrative burdens, visibility and access to networks, and other issues discussed in the following sections.

2.3.1. Restrictions for third countries

Although an associated status entitles third countries to full participation in most calls of the programme – within the limits of their association agreements – there are specific restrictions that apply with regard to governance and access to opportunities. The conditions under which non-EU countries can participate in Horizon Europe are specified in Article 16 of the Horizon Europe Regulation 2021/695 (European Union, 2021). Specifically, Article 16.3 states that *'with the exception of EEA members, acceding countries, candidate*

countries and potential candidates, parts of the Programme may be excluded from an association agreement for a specific country.'

As part of the EEA agreement, EEA countries are entitled to participate under the same conditions as Member States in Framework Programmes (European Commission, 2021c). However, both interviewees from EEA countries have flagged **difficulties in ensuring that the provisions of the EEA agreement are respected** regarding equal treatment to Member States within the programme, with one participant from Iceland highlighting that *'We have to be really proactive in reminding the secretariat and the DGs [Directorate Generals] that we are not an associated country, we are an EEA country.'*

2.3.1.1. Governance restrictions

Whilst associated countries may be observers within programme committees which set out priorities and yearly work programmes within Horizon Europe (e.g. MSCA, missions, clusters, etc.), **they do not gain voting rights.** As expressed in Article 16.2 of the Horizon Europe Regulation 2021/695 (European Union, 2021) *'the agreement (...) (c) does not confer on the third country any decision-making power in respect of the Union programme'*. This matter instigates a range of opinions from participants (See Figure 10). Despite no ability to vote, multiple participants including from the UK and Moldova highlighted that they felt that their voices were heard. The latter expressed moderate satisfaction but remained understanding of the Horizon Europe's Member State-only governance. Two EEA country respondents, from Iceland and Norway were pleased about their ability to shadow certain meetings as a good sign of their equal treatment to Member States.

On the other hand, Turkish and Australian participants noted a lesser satisfaction, *'because we just accept what is given by the European Commission. We are in this*

position, unfortunately' (TR). One Australian interviewee highlighted the added complexity for geographically distant countries and mentioned the significant time commitment, geographic and time zone barriers for their representation, *'If you want to engage in the programme committees and try and influence the direction, it's a huge impost on Australia.'*

Figure 10: Satisfaction with decision-making influence

How satisfied is your country with the level of decision-making influence you hold as an associated state? (1 - Not satisfied; 10 - Very satisfied)

Average: 6.4; Lowest: 2; Highest: 10

If the next Framework Programme (FP10) is to have similar global aspirations for international cooperation as Horizon Europe, and with third countries in favour of such a proposition, it is crucial to find a way to include their viewpoints. An anonymous Turkish participant suggested, *'I think that we should have a more connected group of associated countries. I think **we should stand together**, then we can make our voices heard.'* Participants from Türkiye and the UK would like to see a clearer *'mechanism for taking the views of third countries into consideration'*. (UK). The same UK participant later stated, *'There is the governance point and we won't get votes, but we may want to think about whether we have something like **a joint committee** in addition to do so.'*

Recommendation 8 (EC) Strengthen fora for discussion between third countries, to amplify their voices and share experiences, possibly through the creation of a joint committee.

This joint committee could potentially support the participation of newly associated third countries by providing access to documents and allowing them to stay informed about ongoing developments, especially during transitional arrangements when they cannot attend meetings. Additionally, allowing National Contact Points (NCPs) to observe NCP meetings during the transitional period would be beneficial, as one Canadian participant said they often received documentation indirectly, which was not an efficient way to work.

Recommendation 9 (EC) Include a phased participation of NCPs in meetings during the transitional phase.

2.3.1.2. Restricted calls

Across interviews, Article 22.5 of the Horizon Europe Regulation 2021/695 (European Union, 2021), which allows the EU to **safeguard thematic sensitive calls from associated countries**, such as quantum technology, was brought up by 4 out of 12 respondents (See Figure 4). This restriction, perceived as arbitrary and lacking transparency by some participants, has evoked shared concern and controversy due to its unclear application. One interviewee from Switzerland noted, *'The way it is implemented, or it was implemented, over the course of this current FP9 was difficult to make sense of in some cases.'*

Moreover, an Icelandic respondent reminded that *'we should not be excluded in Article 22.5 according to the EEA agreement.'* A Swiss participant emphasised that *'it limits collaboration with key countries, so it should be at least open to OECD. Otherwise, it creates fragmentation also in Europe.'* The latter expressed a dichotomy between *'limited collaboration, even with like-minded close partners'* while an Australian interviewee

brought up broader concerns about the **reciprocity** of associating to Horizon Europe. It was later shared by an anonymous participant that the EU's approach to sensitive calls appeared to be very **protectionist from their perspective**.

Third countries are not only concerned out of principle but have expressed interest in the themes (usually cybersecurity or quantum) covered by calls restricted under Article 22.5, with one anonymous Turkish participant expressing that *'what is the most alluring part of the programme, I think it's the restricted calls. This is the cherry on top of the ice cream and many third countries/associated countries would like to be part of these restricted calls'* (TR).

These discrepancies were noted by interviewees who ranked the equality of their opportunities compared to those of Member States an average of 6.2 out of 10 (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: Equal opportunities to Member States

Does your country, once associated, have equal opportunities to member states? (1 - Not equal; 10 - Equal)

Average: 6.2; Lowest: 4; Highest: 9

2.3.2. Equality of opportunities and fairness between associated countries

The question of **equality** is also relevant in discussions between third countries. With a formal categorisation system between members of EEA/EFTA (A), acceding, candidate and potential candidate countries (B), European Neighbourhood Policy countries (C), and like-minded countries (D), differences between third countries are **inherent within the design of country categories**. As mentioned above, while EEA countries are to be treated equally to Member States, newly associated countries in category D such as Australia, Canada and New Zealand are currently only allowed to associate to Pillar II.

Figure 12: Equal opportunities with associated Third Countries

Similarly, once associated, does your country have equal opportunities to other associated states? (1 - Not equal; 10 - Equal)

Average: 8.1; Lowest: 7; Highest: 10

In practice, respondents from third countries acknowledge that their access to opportunities, such as funding calls within the programme, was in fact **close to equal**, (see Figure 12) and they expressed general

satisfaction with the equality of opportunities between third countries, as evidenced by an average rating of 8.1 out of 10 (Figure 12).

Leading to the perception of **fairness** - not equality - between association agreements, responses varied across interviewees, with an average of 6.4 out of 10 (see Figure 13). Moldovan participants noted that while agreements may show discrepancies, they were *'fairly equitable.'* One anonymous participant from Türkiye, however, expressed frustration over the political dimension their association had gained (for more details see Box 2), and reported experiencing **a lower level of flexibility** from the EU than other third countries. Furthermore, they remarked that some *'colleagues here in Brussels are having a hard time to ensure their association agreements are in the same line with the other third countries and they simply cannot get this information out of the Commission'* manifesting **'knowingly or unknowingly, an element of lacking transparency'**.

Figure 13: Fairness of association terms between third countries

To what extent are terms of association fair between third countries? (1 - Not fair at all; 10 - Very fair)

Average: 6.4; Lowest: 3; Highest: 9

2.3.3. Practicalities of working on a global scale

With 27 Member States and 24 official languages, navigating **geographic and language challenges** has been central to enhancing collaboration across the EU. These issues are inevitably compounded when considering collaboration with non-European third countries.

One Canadian participant highlighted the overwhelming amount of information received at the start of participation, noting that while the European Commission provides extensive information, **the sheer amount of it can be difficult to manage.** They also pointed out a **language barrier**, where terms like *'exploitation'* have different meanings in general English compared to *'Horizon English.'* The creation of a *'Welcome Pack'* with a glossary translating *'Horizon English'* to standard English and introductory documents was brought up as a way to support newly associated third countries in understanding the components and effectively communicating opportunities to stakeholders.

The **geographic barrier** is an inevitable dimension of globalising collaboration, with one Australian interviewee sharing that *'I think the geographic barrier will always be there for Australia and New Zealand in particular.'* While the digitalisation of collaboration can tackle geographic issues, practical barriers still remain to be addressed. Vastly different **time zones** can hinder third countries' participation in NCP meetings and observation in programme committees, which can be instrumental in optimising the participation of their R&I communities. Taking the examples of current associated third countries, a meeting held at IPM in Brussels would be taking place at 7AM in Toronto, 9PM in Seoul and 1AM in Auckland.

It is realistically not manageable for non-European third countries to attend all meetings, whether virtually or physically - which poses the problem of timely notice to accommodate a long travel and can contradict carbon emission reduction policies - according to an EU-based timetable.

To achieve its global aspirations, it is recommended that Framework Programmes address these challenges with practical solutions, such as carefully timing meetings or hosting them twice or on different timeframes to provide equal opportunities for its global partners.

Recommendation 10 (EC) Take into consideration practical challenges such as time zone and language when engaging with third countries outside of Europe.

2.3.4. Ensuring participation and success of researchers and innovators

According to the Horizon Europe evaluation report (European Commission, 2024a) the processing time for Horizon Europe applications has increased by 23.1 days compared to the same period in Horizon 2020 (FP8), highlighting the growing complexity felt across stakeholders. With vast inequalities in terms of **research support**, from an experienced researcher within a large institution to a small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) inexperienced with the funding model of Horizon Europe, the many months required to draft an application may not be viable for all. Moldovan participants described the daunting nature of the programme *'we are trying to mentor and to guide our researchers how to apply. It is like going straight to the ocean with this programme. You don't know how to swim but you are in the ocean, not even in a lake.'*

Furthermore, **participation rates and success rates are not always synonymous**, and associated third countries present vastly different economies, R&I infrastructures, and overall size. Such factors can foster or inhibit third countries' success in the programme. Participation rates of SMEs were reported to be an internal challenge by Moldovan and Moroccan interviewees, due to small enterprises' lesser involvement in research.

With lower success rates and the deterring effect these can have towards re-applying, respondents from Moldova added that *'SMEs do not have capacities and not only SMEs. Horizon Europe is a very specific programme and it's very competitive, and you have to have a mindset which is more or less European.'*

An Icelandic participant noted that national entities, while greatly benefiting from the programme, faced internal challenges when it comes to the **capacity of their infrastructure to lead a project** *'You need research managers, you need administrative people, you need people to know how to manage the funding properly and so on. Smaller entities, like most of them in Iceland, they do not have those resources, so they can participate as partner.'* Moldovan interviewees expressed a strong feeling of support from the EU but still remarked that *'despite this success, our researchers faced some challenges, such as navigating through complex administrative processes, competing with the well-established EU organisations, and dealing with limited resources and infrastructures.'* and concluded that *'we really need to be competitive and we don't have capability or the training to write the project.'*

Looking ahead, **interviewees from third countries unanimously wish for the application process to be simplified**. One interviewee from Iceland recommended to *'Make it simple for applicants to apply'* as *'we have to be able to fund certain amount of applications for it to be viable for researchers to spend their time in just applying'*.

Moldovan participants called for efforts to *'provide clear guidelines and to offer better support throughout the project lifecycle.'* Comments such as *'Just less bureaucracy would be great.'* (AU) and the desire for *'a simplified version of the Framework 9'* (IS) reflect a widespread demand for **reducing administrative burdens** in the next Framework Programme.

Additionally, one anonymous Turkish participant would be in support of a uniform application process across programmes: *'you don't want to learn all the application procedures for all the programmes. You want to have one more or less similar application form and then you want to apply.'*

Recommendation 11 (EC) Streamline and simplify the application process for prospective beneficiaries, supporting participation across all organisations (including SMEs) and regions from third countries.

In line with **capacity building** for excellent science, several participants mentioned **Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area (WIDERA)** – a sub-programme of Horizon Europe aiming to improve research and innovation capacity for countries lagging behind. Respondents from Türkiye and Moldova would like to continue being involved in Widening calls and believe these are still needed to address existing disparities between Western and Eastern Europe. On the other hand, respondents from the UK and Switzerland have expressed interest in evaluating the effectiveness of the WIDERA initiative, seeking evidence of its practical impact.

2.3.5. Consortia and networks

Beyond internal challenges, third countries may face obstacles if their **networks** (i.e. connections with universities, civil, and industry partners) are not as developed as others, which can limit their access to opportunities where longstanding partners systematically connect. A participant from Morocco noted: *'You cannot be alone and just wake up the morning and say, OK, I will send a proposal to Horizon Europe now. It needs lots of connections and lots of trainings, so it's not something easy mainly for the young researchers.'*

Looking to improve training and awareness of researchers and industry, a participant from Morocco stated that their participation was in a way, passive and dependent on existing consortia's invitation, remarking that *'perhaps there is a lack of awareness from these European countries and big consortia that apply for projects regarding the capacity of Morocco to join these specific calls.'*

One anonymous Turkish interviewee added that **presence in Brussels is imperative**: *'It is very difficult to be heard and to prove yourself that you are worthy of these funding', 'this is a very closed club and it's very difficult to get in, especially if you don't have any contact, any champion that is cheering for you from within.'* but remarked as well that representation and promotion of Turkish actors requires internal initiative *'It's difficult because the blame's also partly on us because we don't have these established representation mechanisms as a country.'*

This discussion suggests the need for further efforts to strengthen the visibility of third countries' research and innovation communities amongst networks and in Brussels. As mentioned in **Recommendation 8**, strengthening fora for discussion between third countries and amplifying their voices could potentially be achieved through the creation of a joint committee.

2.3.6. Synergies and predictability

An additional barrier to participation for third countries in Horizon Europe is the implementation of inter-programme synergies. An Icelandic respondent referred to this as a **'Lego approach'** emphasizing its pursuit for fluidity of opportunities across EU programmes such as Horizon Europe, LIFE, and Digital Europe. As outlined in the 2023–2025 Horizon Europe work programme for Cluster 1 'Health', there is a rising impetus for applicants to consider synergies with, for example, the EU4Health programme to *'facilitate the uptake, scaling-up and deployment of health innovations in healthcare systems and clinical practice'* (European Commission, 2024b).

Currently, only three third countries interviewed as part of this study (Norway, Iceland, and Moldova) are associated to EU4Health, the programme focused on reinforcing crisis preparedness in the EU (European Commission, n.d.b).

A Turkish respondent highlighted that while synergies are beneficial and can result in higher impact projects with pathways for scaling up, **they are not always enabling for third countries**. They stated that *'Synergy should be more realistic for the other associated countries, through [Instrument for Pre-accession Assistance] IPA, [European Bank for Reconstruction and Development] EBRD, [European Investment Bank] EIB.'* Türkiye as a candidate country is part of the Instrument for Pre-accession Assistance (IPA III), which as participants expressed, had been instrumental in developing EU innovative projects. Similarly, respondents from EEA countries and Switzerland expressed concerns that synergies might hinder third countries' participation. One interviewee from Iceland noted *'That kind of modularization is not very good for a small country like Iceland because we are not, of course, participating in all of the programmes the EU has.'*

To address these concerns, it is recommended that synergies be critically evaluated if included in FP10, ensuring they **do not unfairly impair third countries' participation** (See **Recommendation 12**, arising from discussion in Sections 2.1.3 and 2.3.6). This discussion opens up broader considerations about the predictability of instruments within the programme. While interviewees from Switzerland and Iceland acknowledge the need for some flexibility, they caution against the addition of new instruments or strategic areas that could complicate participation, especially after they have associated *'we don't want addition of new instruments or of new strategic areas throughout programme feeding off existing instruments that we like.'* (CH, anonymous). As a UK participant noted, *'No one wants a situation where you've signed up to something and what you get out of it's not what you signed up for or not what you were promised by the start of that discussion.'*

Recommendation 12 (EC) Ensure the inclusion of third countries' voices at the design stage of the Framework Programme to guarantee realistic synergies and access to key programme pillars.

2.4. Challenges in perspective

Despite challenges discussed in this section, participants reported an **overall satisfaction with FP9**, expressing that they were happy with the programme and saw a very positive response from their research and innovation communities. This is particularly true in relation to higher participation and success rates in Türkiye, Moldova, Switzerland, and Norway. Additionally, participants from Morocco, Norway, and the UK emphasized good programme alignment with national priorities (see also Figure 3), with interviewees from the UK reminding that they had participated in the design of FP9.

'I do not agree with those people who criticise very harshly FP9', concluded one anonymous Turkish participant.

III. Looking towards Framework Programme 10

'I think there's something for everyone in this programme and I think that we should keep that that festival of opportunities, that festival of calls.'
(TR, anonymous)

The European Commission's proposal for FP10, expected to be unveiled in the summer of 2025, will shape the future direction and priorities of this pivotal initiative. As we anticipate the next Framework Programme set to span 2028–2034, interview participants were invited to share their insights and expectations for the programme.

3.1. Intention to associate to FP10

Interviewees were asked whether their country was looking to associate to the next programme. No respondent answered negatively, although half of them were cautious about indicating their intention to associate in the absence of an official government position. Interviewees from the United Kingdom, Norway, Morocco, Canada, and Australia stated, at the time of the interviews (March to October 2024), that it was **too early to say**, with one participant from Norway mentioning that they were preparing to associate. The remaining participants – from Switzerland, Iceland, Türkiye and Moldova – answered a clear **'yes'**, indicating full intent at the time of the interviews.

3.2. Evolution or Revolution?

When asked if an **evolution** or **revolution** should take place for FP10, all respondents favoured an evolution, ensuring **stability and predictability**, as well as preserving instruments that have shown high success. All the more, one Swiss participant stated that *'Stability would be better, especially when it comes to maintaining tried-and-tested instruments like the ERC and MSCA.'* Moldovan participants proposed an *'Evolution through revolution'* highlighting that a larger transformative goal must be pursued but can be achieved through gradual improvement to avoid resistance associated with radical change.

3.3. What should continue? What should change?

Interviewees were also invited to provide opinions on FP9's structure and instruments, sharing what should continue and what should change. With this information increasingly available through third countries' and networks' position papers, this section provides a short summary of points of satisfaction and concern expressed during interviews.

Pillar I: Across interviews, Pillar I was mentioned as an element to continue 100% of the time. There was general agreement among respondents from the UK, Türkiye, Switzerland, and Australia that investments in mobility and infrastructure as well as the proven and competitive bottom-up approach within the ERC and MSCA were positive and important to keep in FP10.

Pillar II: Pillar II was recommended to continue by participants as an accessible and attractive funding model with a strong focus on challenge-driven investment. However, a few interviewees noted that the thematic prioritisation of clusters could be reassessed. Cluster 6 'Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment', in particular, was highlighted as an area for review. With a view to address worldwide problems, some participants advocate for greater integration of global perspectives and recognition of non EU-centric interests.

Pillar III: Pillar III was more controversial with participants keen to see changes from its current implementation, while recognising the necessity of investment in industry. One participant from Türkiye supports a return to a structure closer to Fast Track to Innovation from Horizon 2020, while a British counterpart emphasized the need for better funding in this area. Noting the importance of fostering competition, Moldovan participants called for greater inclusion of SMEs within Framework Programmes, in hopes to support unicorn companies.

EU missions: While they provide a pathway to including a variety of actors and activities within Horizon Europe bids, some participants remarked that the scope of EU Missions went too far beyond R&I. Interviewees expressed that the aims of missions should be clearer and more relevant to the Framework Programme.

3.4. Enhancing inclusivity and clear messaging in Horizon Europe

In reflecting on the experiences of third countries participating in Horizon Europe, it is evident that the programme has made a step change towards a more global research and innovation environment. However, some interviewees have expressed a desire for clearer communication regarding the aspirations of Framework Programmes and a more explicit articulation of the balance between openness and necessary restrictions, encapsulated in the phrase *'as open as possible and as closed as necessary.'*

An Australian respondent highlighted that *'The programme has evolved to involve associated countries, but in essence it is still about Europe and Europe's competitiveness, and so that bleeds through in everything, all the language, all of the ways it's structured, and so it's not actually designed to be an international programme in that sense.'* Comparisons to Horizon 2020 reveal a perceived lack of clarity in Horizon Europe's messaging about its purpose. As one Australian respondent noted: *'I just feel like this it hasn't been able to have as clear a message about its purpose as Horizon 2020 was able to have.'*

Conversely, despite noting that their country's interests are perceived not to be well represented in the design of FP9 (rating it a 6 out of 10, see Figure 7), Moldovan respondents demonstrated a more nuanced understanding, *'This programme is mainly for improving the EU innovative ecosystem to be the best in the world. That is why everything that is done, is done for the EU, so it's understandable.'*

IV. Recommendations

Based on evidence gathered from interviews, we propose a set of recommendations summarized below aimed at enhancing the association process and the participation of third countries in the upcoming Framework Programme. As illustrated in the report, these recommendations provide a comprehensive overview of key points for improvement.

Notably, many of these recommendations are directed towards the European Commission. However, three of these recommendations (**Recommendation 1, Recommendation 7, and Recommendation 8**) are applicable to third countries themselves, indicating that there is scope for collaboration and progress towards a shared future, requiring efforts from both sides.

Recommendation 1 (3rd) When considering association, take into account both monetary and non-monetary benefits to the economy and the society, including the research and innovation (R&I) community.

Recommendation 2 (EC) Provide more clarity and transparency for third countries about association terms, especially financial, governance and restrictions.

Recommendation 3 (EC) Offer financial safeguards opportunities to all third countries, to limit the risk of financial exposure related to participation.

Recommendation 4 (EC) Consider allowing association to more than Pillar II to all countries from D category.

Recommendation 5 (EC) Provide further consideration for country categorisation in the next Framework Programme (e.g. to better reflect historical partnerships).

Recommendation 6 (EC) Ensure that FP10 is established early enough for third countries to associate in a timely manner, preferably to initiate participation at the start of the programme.

Recommendation 7 (3rd) Offer match-funding (e.g. guarantee or direct funding) mechanisms to mitigate impacts of delays on participation.

Recommendation 8 (3rd) Strengthen fora for discussion between third countries, to amplify their voices and share experiences, possibly through the creation of a joint committee.

Recommendation 9 (EC) Include a phased participation of NCPs in meetings during the transitional phase.

Recommendation 10 (EC) Take into consideration practical challenges such as time zone and language when engaging with third countries outside of Europe.

Recommendation 11 (EC) Streamline and simplify the application process for prospective beneficiaries, supporting participation across all organisations (including SMEs) and regions from third countries.

Recommendation 12 (EC) Ensure the inclusion of third countries' voices at the design stage of the Framework Programme to guarantee realistic synergies and access to key programme pillars.

Since opening up to international partners, Framework Programmes in general and Horizon Europe in particular have become tools of **science diplomacy** (European Commission, 2025). The inherent tension between international cooperation and competition is likely to continue. Our hope is that this report and its findings will encourage effective communication and multilateral dialogue between the European Commission and third countries, aimed at identifying and implementing mutually beneficial solutions for all parties involved in the largest international R&I framework going forward.

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